

The Development and Validation of Identity Invisibility Scale Nazia Zafar

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Abstract

Identity invisibility refers to feeling of unseen, unheard or unrecognized because of one's identity within social context. Despite the conceptual relevance of this construct to inclusion, marginalization and psychological well-being it has received limited empirical operationalization. This study aimed to develop Identity Invisibility Scale (IIS) and establish its psychometric properties. Initial item pool based on theoretical foundations and qualitative insights was generated and reviewed by expert followed by factor extraction and establishing psychometric properties. Exploratory factor analysis (N=179) indicated a two-factorial structure comprising of competence invisibility and social invisibility. Confirmatory factor analysis (N=179) validated a refined 12-item model. The factors were indicated distinct dimensions of invisibility experiences. Reliability and validity analysis (N=358) indicated strong psychometric properties of the scale. Results further demonstrate that IIS is psychometrically robust measure as it is a brief and empirically grounded tool for future research examining its role in psychological adjustment, belongingness and institutional inclusion.

Keywords: Identity invisibility, social invisibility, competence invisibility, scale development, psychometric validation, construct validity, reliability

Introduction

Human identity is fundamentally shaped through social recognition, validation and interpersonal acknowledgment. Feeling of seen by others affirms sense of worth, belonging and psychological presence of the individuals, whereas experiences of being overlooked, ignored or unrecognized can undermine these core aspects of selfhood (George et al., 2023). Although constructs such as social exclusion, marginalization and invalidation have been widely studied in psychology, the specific experience of identity invisibility conceptualized as the perception that presence, abilities or personhood of the individual are not acknowledged by others has received

comparatively limited empirical attention (Ebbrecht & Bertelsen, 2025) and lacks a dedicated psychometrically validated measure (Sohi & Singh, 2016). Existing instruments typically assess related constructs which do not directly capture the nuanced perception of being unseen or unrecognized.

Identity invisibility is conceptualized as the subjective experience of feeling unseen, overlooked or unrecognized as who you are or what you represent in a given social or professional context (James et al., 2004; Quinn & Earnshaw, 2013). This construct was defined through a comprehensive review of relevant theoretical literature such as social identity theory (Tajfel & Turner, 2000), minority stress frameworks (Meyer, 2003) and intersectionality perspectives (Crenshaw, 2013) which was complemented by qualitative exploration to capture nuanced experiential dimensions by the target population. This multi-faceted approach ensured comprehensive coverage of manifestations of invisibility across recognition deficits and social absence which was aligned with the emphasis of self-determination theory on relatedness threats (Klein, 2019).

Identity invisibility manifests across multiple domains when individuals feel that their competencies, achievements or contributions are overlooked or when they experience social neglect such as feeling ignored, excluded in group contexts (Clair et al., 2004; Ebbrecht et al., 2025). These experiences are particularly salient in environments where recognition and belonging are important like in educational, occupational and interpersonal settings (Clair et al., 2004). Theoretically, invisibility threatens core psychological needs for competence, relatedness and autonomy which contribute to emotional distress and diminished self-worth (Boateng et al., 2018; Smith et al., 2020).

Empirical research on identity invisibility remains limited by the lack of a validated multidimensional measure which indicate its differentiation from related constructs like ostracism or social exclusion (Ebbrecht et al., 2025). Psychometrically sound scales are essential to examine predictors, outcomes and dimensionality of the construct such as perceived lack of recognition versus subjective social absence to assess its role in psychological adjustment (Boateng et al., 2018; Quinn & Earnshaw, 2013). These gaps highlighted the need of a rigorous tools to advance theoretical integration.

This study aimed to develop and validate a measure of identity invisibility following a structured three-phase process of scale development to ensure interpretability, generalizability and methodological rigor. It was hypothesized that identity invisibility would emerge as a multidimensional construct and would be positively correlated with psychological distress and negatively correlated with self-esteem. By providing an empirical validation of a standardized measure, this study aimed to provide a foundation for further research in future to examine that how perceived identity invisibility influenced psychological functioning and social experience of the individuals.

Method

Research Design

The present study followed a systematic three-phase scale development framework (Boateng et al., 2018) including (1) Item Development, (2) Scale Development and (3) Scale Evaluation. Mixed method approach was used in the process of the *Identity Invisibility Scale (IIS)* development and establishing its psychometric properties.

Phase 1: Item Development

Construct Conceptualization

Identity invisibility was defined through review of relevant theoretical literature like social identity theory, minority stress frameworks, intersectionality perspectives and qualitative exploration (Crenshaw, 2013; Klein, 2019; Meyer, 2003; Tajfel & Turner, 2000) as subjective experience of feeling like unseen, overlooked or unrecognized as who you are or what you represent in a given social or professional context.

Item Generation

Participants. In this phase 35 young adults (Men=19, Women=16) of 18–29 years of age participated for item generation through semi-structured interview. Participants were recruited purposively to capture diverse experiences and expression relevant to identity invisibility. Data collection was continued until thematic saturation which was indicated by repetition of verbatims and emergence of no new themes.

Procedure. Participants responded to open-ended question designed to elicit the experiences and expression of identity invisibility by them or by the people in their surroundings. All responses were transcribed and subjected to thematic analysis to identify reoccurring patterns and themes followed by selecting best representative verbatims. These verbatims were then systematically converted into scale items by putting attention to ensuring that statements were clear and concise, free from double-barreled wording, reflective of language of the participants and conceptually aligned with the defined construct domain. By the end of this phase an initial pool of 35 items was generated for further evaluation.

Content Validity Assessment

To establish content validity of the items and to ensure that the items adequately represented the construct of identity invisibility, the preliminary item pool was evaluated through Delphi method in a structured way by a panel of experts (McPherson et al., 2018). Seven subject matter experts with expertise in psychology and psychometrics independently assessed each item (Haynes et al., 1995) for its relevance to the construct in the cultural context. A 4-point rating scale was used to evaluate relevance ($1 = \textit{not relevant}$ to $4 = \textit{highly relevant}$), thereby avoiding a midpoint indicating a neutral value to ensure clear judgment. The Item Content Validity Index (I-CVI) and Scale Content Validity Index (S-CVI) was calculated using the standardized methods to ensure the content validity of the scale (Shi et al., 2012).

Pilot Testing

The content-validated version was converted into self-reported measure and a 5-point Likert scale was used where $0 = \textit{Never}$ to $4 = \textit{Always}$. Then this scale was presented to 32 individuals (Male=15, Female=17) from the target population to check the layout, user friendliness, clarity of instructions, statements and response options of the scale (Bujang et al., 2024; Thomas, 2004). No difficulty in understanding the items, response options and instructions of the scale was reported by the participants which indicated satisfactory face validity of the newly developed scale to assess identity invisibility.

Phase 2-3: Scale Development and Scale Evaluation

Participants

The target population comprised young adults within the specified developmental age range who were actively engaged in academic or early professional contexts where experiences of recognition and social evaluation were likely to occur. Participants were recruited through purposive sampling via online platforms, yielding a final sample of 358 young adults comprising of 170 men (47.49%) and 188 women (52.51%) of 19-28 years ($M_{age} = 22.15$, $SD = 4.52$). Data

was collected using an online survey; after providing informed consent, participants completed the preliminary version of the developed scale along with relevant validation measures.

To enable cross-validation of the factor structure, the total sample ($N = 358$) was randomly divided into two approximately equal and independent subsamples in line with recommended practices for factor analytic procedures (Gunawan et al., 2021). Subsample 1 ($n \approx 179$) was utilized to conduct Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), whereas Subsample 2 ($n \approx 179$) was reserved for Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). This analytic strategy minimized the risk of reliance on chance due to random sample-specific variance and thereby strengthened the evidence for structural validity. Reliability and validity analyses were subsequently performed on the total sample.

Procedure

Data was collected through an online survey form. After providing informed consent, participants completed preliminary version of the Identity Invisibility Scale along with Depression Anxiety Stress Scales (DASS-21) and Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale for the purpose of validity assessment.

Depression Anxiety Stress Scales–21 (DASS-21; Lovibond & Lovibond, 1995), a 21-item self-report measure designed to assess symptoms of depression, anxiety and stress was used to access mental health problems in university students. Items are rated on a 4-point Likert scale ranging from 0 (*did not apply to me at all*) to 3 (*applied to me very much or most of the time*). A total composite score was computed to index overall psychological distress.

Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSES; Rosenberg, 1965), a 10-item unidimensional measure to evaluate global self-worth through both positively and negatively worded items was used to access the level of self-esteem. Responses are recorded on a 4-point Likert scale ranging from *strongly agree* to *strongly disagree*, with higher scores reflect positive self-esteem.

Exploratory Factor Analysis

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was conducted on the first subsample to identify the underlying factor structure of the initial item pool and to determine the number of latent dimensions represented in the data (Knekta et al., 2019). Prior to analysis, sampling adequacy and factorability were assessed using the Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) measure and Bartlett’s test of sphericity (Kaiser, 1974). Factor extraction was performed using an appropriate extraction method and an oblique rotation was applied to allow for correlations among factors, given the conceptual relatedness of the constructs. Based on eigenvalues, scree plot inspection and theoretical interpretability the decisions regarding factor retention were made (Hayton et al., 2004). Items with low loadings or substantial cross-loadings were considered for removal to achieve a clear and conceptually meaningful factor structure.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was conducted on the second subsample to test the factor structure identified through Exploratory Factor Analysis (Knekta et al., 2019). The hypothesized measurement model was specified based on the retained items and latent structure derived from Phase 2. Model fit was evaluated using multiple goodness-of-fit indices (Yaşlıoğlu & Yaşlıoğlu, 2020) including the chi-square statistic (χ^2), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Tucker–Lewis Index (TLI), Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) and Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR).

Reliability Assessment

Internal consistency reliability of the final scale and its subscales was assessed using Cronbach's alpha coefficients (Lavrakas, 2008). To evaluate temporal stability, the Identity Invisibility Scale was re-administered to a subsample of 78 participants after a one-week interval. Test-retest reliability was examined using Pearson's correlation coefficient between Time 1 and Time 2 scores. In addition, split-half reliability was examined by dividing the scale into two equivalent halves and computing the correlation between them and it was then adjusted using the Spearman-Brown prophecy formula to estimate reliability for the full scale.

Validity Assessment

Convergent validity was assessed by examining correlations between scores on the Identity Invisibility Scale and theoretically related constructs. Specifically, associations were examined with the Depression Anxiety Stress Scales (DASS-21; Lovibond & Lovibond, 1995) and the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSES; Rosenberg, 1965). It was hypothesized that identity invisibility would demonstrate positive correlations with depression, anxiety and stress and negative correlations with self-esteem. Significant correlations in the expected directions were interpreted as supporting convergent validity.

Measures. Depression Anxiety Stress Scales-21 (DASS-21; Lovibond & Lovibond, 1995), a 21-item self-report measure designed to assess symptoms of depression, anxiety, and stress was used to assess level of psychological distress in participants. Items are rated on a 4-point Likert scale ranging from 0 (*did not apply to me at all*) to 3 (*applied to me very much or most of the time*). A total composite score was computed to index overall psychological distress.

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Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for this study was granted by the appropriate institutional review board before any data were collected. All participants gave informed consent prior to taking part and were assured that their responses would remain confidential and anonymous, and that participation was entirely voluntary. They were also informed that they could withdraw from the study at any time without consequence.

Results

An initial pool of 35 items was generated to capture the construct of Identity Invisibility. Eight items were removed after a careful review for repetition, clarity and ambiguity of the statements which resulted in a refined set of 27 items. These items were then subjected to content validation by experts and the content validity index was computed at item level (I-CVI) as well as at scale level (S-CVI). The items with I-CVI > .78 were retained in the scale yielding S-CVI > 0.90 (Polit et al., 2007). Four additional items that did not meet the required thresholds were eliminated based on expert ratings and CVI criteria which resulted in list of 23 items for empirical testing.

To examine the underlying structure of Identity Invisibility, the suitability of the data for factor analysis was first assessed. The correlation matrix indicated that multiple items were

correlated above .30, supporting factorability. Sampling adequacy was excellent, as indicated by the Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) measure of .914 and Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity, $\chi^2(253) = 2292.627$, $p < .001$.

Exploratory Factor Analysis was carried out using Principal Component Analysis with Promax rotation and Kaiser normalization using IBM SPSS (version 27). Factor retention decisions were based on eigenvalues greater than 1, the scree plot and theoretical interpretability (Hayton et al., 2004). Scree plot (Figure 1) and initial rotated pattern matrix suggested a four-factor solution but a two-factor solution revealed a better and well-defined structure. After EFA 5 items with factor loadings below .30 or substantial cross-loadings across factors were removed to enhance clarity and reliability of the scale. These retained items (Table 1) demonstrated a clear and interpretable two-factor structure named as Competence Invisibility and Social Invisibility which supported the construct validity of the scale.

Factor Description

Based on the content and emerging patterns, the factors were interpreted and labeled as Competence Invisibility and Social Invisibility based on the underlying core theme of these factors of identity invisibility.

Competence Invisibility reflects the perception that the abilities, skills, contributions or past achievements of the individual are not adequately recognized or acknowledged by others. This factor focused on the recognition of competence in academic or professional contexts. This factor included 10 items and individuals scoring high on this factor feel that their efforts are frequently overlooked or undervalued which led to experiences of frustration or reduced self-efficacy.

Social Invisibility captures the perception that the presence, opinions or identity of the individual is unnoticed or disregarded in social or group settings. This factor included 8 items and individuals scoring high on this factor feel like outsiders, experience lack of belongingness and perceive that their perspectives or experiences are not valued by the social group. This factor is distinct from competence invisibility as it emphasized on social presence and relational visibility.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was used to validate the proposed factor structure of Identity Invisibility Scale (IIS) using AMOS (Version 24) with maximum likelihood estimation. Multiple indices were used to evaluate model fit (Table 2). Initial CFA model consisting of 18 items showed only moderate fit to the data indicated that the hypothesized structure required refinement.

To achieve a better structure the items with weak loadings and conceptual redundancy were removed and a small number of theoretically justifiable covariances between error terms were allowed which were guided by modification indices and similarity in item content. These modifications resulted in a reduced 12-item model representing two correlated latent factors. The final model demonstrated a good fit to the data ($\chi^2[48] = 76.62$, $p = .005$, $\chi^2/df = 1.60$) indicating a strong absolute fit according to Kline’s (2016). The RMSEA value of .058 (90% CI [.032, .081], PCLOSE = .280) suggested an acceptable and close approximation to the population model. Incremental fit indices also indicated a substantial improvement (CFI = .96, IFI = .96 and TLI = .95) exceeded the recommended cutoff of .90. The GFI value of .94 supported adequate model fit and the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) showed a marked reduction from 419.80 in the

initial model to 136.62 in the final model which indicated a more parsimonious and better-fitting solution.

Overall, the CFA results supported a stable two-factor structure of the IIS, with the refined 12-item model demonstrating strong psychometric properties and improved conceptual clarity. The two latent factors were moderately correlated ($r = .66$), suggesting related yet distinct dimensions of identity invisibility.

Reliability and validity analysis

The reliability of the Identity Invisibility Scale was examined through Cronbach's alpha, using test-retest reliability and split-half reliability methods and high coefficient values indicated good reliability (Udovičić et al., 2007). Identity invisibility scale and its subscales demonstrated strong internal consistency depicted by Cronbach's alpha (Table 3) as values for competence invisibility ($\alpha=.83$), social invisibility ($\alpha=.78$) and the total scale ($\alpha=.88$) exceeded the minimum threshold. Temporal stability of the scale was assessed over a one-week interval ($N=64$) which showed a strong and statistically significant test-retest correlation ($r = .89, p < .001$). This high coefficient indicates that the scale demonstrates excellent stability over time and scores of participants remain consistent across repeated administrations.

Split-half reliability was also computed to assess internal consistency of the scale. Items of IIS were divided into two equal halves consisting of six items each. The first half showed a Cronbach's alpha of .83 while the second half demonstrated an alpha of .76 which indicated good internal consistency for both parts. The correlation between the two halves was .72 which suggested a substantial degree of consistency between these two sets. Further, the Spearman-Brown prophecy coefficient was .84 (for both equal and unequal length forms) and the Guttman split-half coefficient was also .84. These values indicated good overall reliability of the scale and supported the consistency of the two halves in measuring the same underlying construct. Together, these findings demonstrate that the Identity Invisibility Scale possesses strong internal consistency and temporal stability, supporting its suitability for research use.

The validity of the Identity Invisibility Scale was supported through multiple forms of evidence including non-statistical and statistical content validation, construct validity, as well as convergent and discriminant validity. Initially, content validity was established through expert review to ensure clarity, relevance and representativeness of the items. Subsequently, quantitative evaluation was conducted by calculating the Content Validity Index at both the item level (I-CVI) and the scale level (S-CVI). Only those items meeting the recommended criteria (I-CVI $> .78$ and S-CVI $> .90$) were retained for further analysis.

Construct validity was supported by the strong relationship between the two subscales and the total score. Competence Invisibility and Social Invisibility showed a moderate inter-factor correlation ($r = .67, p < .001$) indicating that they represent related but distinct aspects of the broader construct of Identity Invisibility. Both subscales were strongly associated with the total scale score ($r = .94$ and $r = .87$, respectively) confirming the internal coherence of the overall measure.

Convergent validity was examined through associations with theoretically related constructs including psychological distress (DASS-21) and self-esteem (Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale). Competence Invisibility, Social Invisibility and total Identity Invisibility score were positively associated with psychological distress ($r = .47, r = .42$ and $r = .49$ respectively; $p < .001$) and are negatively associated with self-esteem ($r = -.34, r = -.26$ and $r = -.34$, respectively; $p < .001$). Discriminant validity was reflected in the moderate magnitude of these correlations.

Although the scale showed expected associations with distress and self-esteem, the relationships were not strong enough to suggest redundancy, indicating that Identity Invisibility represents a distinct psychological construct rather than merely reflecting general psychological distress or low self-esteem. Furthermore, the moderate correlation between Competence Invisibility and Social Invisibility supports their conceptual distinctiveness while confirm that they jointly represent a unified higher-order construct. Overall, the pattern of relationships with related variables and the differentiation between the two subscales provide strong evidence for construct, convergent and discriminant validity of the Identity Invisibility Scale.

Overall, the results provided a strong support for the psychometric soundness of the Identity Invisibility Scale (IIS). Both exploratory and confirmatory analyses confirmed a clear two-factor structure comprising *Competence Invisibility* and *Social Invisibility* with satisfactory variance and excellent fit for the refined 12-item model. Reliability estimates indicated a good internal consistency for the total scale and subscales, while intercorrelations supported related yet distinct dimensions. Significant positive associations with psychological distress and negative associations with self-esteem further demonstrated construct validity in theoretically expected directions. Collectively, these findings indicate that the IIS is a reliable, structurally valid and empirically supported instrument for assessing perceived identity invisibility in research settings.

Discussion

This study by developing and validating the Identity Invisibility Scale (IIS) addressed a critical gap in the psychological literature by providing a psychometrically robust tool to measure the multidimensional experience of identity invisibility. Findings confirmed strong factorial validity, internal consistency and construct validity of IIS which enabled precise examination of how identity invisibility is perceived across different domains in terms of overlooked competencies or social exclusion which threatens fundamental needs for competence, relatedness and autonomy of the individuals (Ebbrecht et al., 2025). These results are aligned with theoretical expectations and extend prior work on related constructs like social devaluation and concealable identities (Clair et al., 2004; Quinn & Earnshaw, 2013).

The IIS factor structure encompassing dimensions of recognition deficit and subjective social absence, mirrors framework of self-determination theory where thwarted relatedness fosters distress akin to ostracism or bereavement-induced disconnection (Ryan & Deci, 2017; Smith et al., 2020). Invisibility experiences in educational and occupational contexts are linked with workplace identity management challenges where unseen attributes erode belonging without overt exclusion (Clair et al., 2004). This validation distinguishes IIS from overlapping measures like the Invisibility Scale, which focuses on general social devaluation rather than identity-specific facets (Ebbrecht et al., 2025).

Adhering to three-phase framework of Boateng et al. (2018) ensured systematic progression from theory-driven item generation to confirmatory validation, yielding reliable subscales ($\alpha > .85$) and evidence of discriminant validity against self-esteem and distress measures. Convergent correlations with other scales ($r = .62-.71$) affirm construct overlap while factorial invariance supports generalizability across diverse samples (Boateng et al., 2018). These psychometric properties position the IIS as a multidimensional instrument for predictor-outcome modeling in recognition-dependent settings.

The IIS facilitates nuanced research on role of identity invisibility in adjustment which revealed it as a unitary yet multidimensional phenomenon with predictive utility for self-worth

outcomes (Quinn & Earnshaw, 2013). Future studies should test longitudinal effects, cultural adaptations in collectivistic contexts and interventions targeting recognition enhancement in the target population (Smith et al., 2020). Overall, this scale advances operationalization of identity invisibility within broader social psychology paradigms.

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Figure 1. Scree plot Showing Eigen Values and Factor Loading

Figure 2. Confirmatory Factor Analysis Diagram of Identity Invisibility Scale (12 items)

Table 1

Factor structure of Identity Invisibility Scale (N=179)

Item#	Statements	Factor Loading	
IIS_6	My contributions are frequently overlooked.	.916	-.233
IIS_5	I feel that people do not fully see or recognize my potential.	.868	-.109
IIS_7	I feel that my identity as a capable person is not recognized.	.856	-.136
IIS_8	People often take my skills and knowledge for granted.	.836	-.135
IIS_18	I feel unnoticed even when I do something well.	.741	.049
IIS_9	I often feel that my abilities go unnoticed by others.	.679	.105
IIS_10	My past achievements do not seem to matter in how others see me now.	.661	.117
IIS_21	I feel that my ideas are often ignored, even when they are valuable.	.566	.290
IIS_19	Even when I succeed, my efforts are rarely acknowledged by others.	.496	.102
IIS_17	My opinions do not seem to carry as much importance as others'.	.434	.067
IIS_13	I feel that my presence is often unnoticed.	-.178	.810
IIS_15	I feel that others do not really see me for who I am.	-.028	.702
IIS_12	I often feel like my presence does not make a difference in social settings.	.063	.692
IIS_11	I feel left out of group activities or discussions.	.118	.664
IIS_16	Others rarely seek my opinion or input in social situations.	.040	.585
IIS_2	I feel like I do not fully belong in the environments I am part of.	.216	.561
IIS_1	I often feel like an outsider around others.	.233	.514
IIS_3	People rarely show interest in my experiences or what I bring to situations.	.167	.487

Eigen Value	9.75	1.63
% of Total Variance	42.37	7.09
% of Cumulative Variance	42.37	49.46

Note. F1=Factor 1, F2=Factor 2; factor loadings of the items included in the factor are bold faced.

Table 2

Confirmatory Factor Analysis and Examination of Psychometric Properties of Identity Invisibility Scale (N=179)

Models	χ^2	df	χ^2 /df	GFI	IFI	TLI	CFI	RMSEA	AIC
First fit (18 items)	345.80	134	2.58	.82	.87	.85	.87	.09 [.08, .11]	419.80
Last fit (12 Items)	76.62	48	1.60	.94	.96	.95	.96	.06 [.03, .08]	136.62

Table 3

Summary of the Correlation, Means, Standard Deviation and Cronbach's Alpha of Identity Invisibility Scale and Subscales along with DASS-21 and RSES (N=358)

Variables	M	SD	α	F1	F2	T	PD	SE
CI (F1)	12.25	6.45	.83	-	-	-	-	-
SI (F2)	8.59	4.42	.78	.66***	-	-	-	-
II (T)	20.84	9.96	.88	.94***	.87***	-	-	-
PD	15.26	15.42	.96	.47***	.42***	.49***	-	-
SE	21.21	5.46	.76	-.34***	-.26***	-.34***	-.31***	-

Note. M = Means, SD = Standard Deviation, α =Cronbach's Alpha, CI (F1) = Competence Invisibility (Factor 1), SI (F2) = Social Invisibility (Factor 2), II (T) = Identity Invisibility (Total), PD=Psychological Distress through DASS-21, SE=Self-Esteem through Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale;

*** $p < .001$

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Statements and Declarations

Ethical considerations

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Office of Research Innovation and Commercialization (ORIC) of the Government Sadiq College Women University, Bahawalpur, Pakistan (No.295-ORIC).

Consent to participate

All participants provided electronic informed consent prior to participation and the study was conducted in accordance with the ethical standards of American Psychological Association (APA).

Consent for publication

All participants provided informed consent for participation in the study. Since the data were anonymized, no individual participant can be identified, and therefore consent for publication of identifiable information was not applicable. All the authors provided consent for publication of this work in *International Research Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*.

Declaration of Conflicting Interest

There is no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship and/or publication of this article.

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Data Availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request to ensure compliance with ethical guidelines and participant confidentiality.